

The presence approach: *Reflections on the role of empathy and ‘being present’ in youth mentoring relationships*

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Empathy

- Complex relational process (Spencer, 2017).
- **Three parts of Empathy** (Ellison et al., 2011, p. 133)
 - A) An emotional response to the experiences of others
 - B) A capacity for taking the other's person's perspective
 - C) An ability to regulate one's own emotional responses to the experiences of the other person in a way that allows for the mobilization of compassionate and responsive helping behavior

Relationships in client-centered social services

- (Quality) Relationship is the most important thing
- Rogers (1959): Empathy, Authenticity and Positive Regard
- Theory: Ryan (1991, 1993): Social interventions aim to **facilitate basic human needs** in relatedness, autonomy and competence **through quality supportive growth-promoting relationships** for positive development, well-being and change in clients.
- Relationships are complex and can be challenging
- Relationship-based interventions: A (social) worker is the key (Spencer, 2012, Brumovská, Seidlová Málková, 2010, Lambert, Barley, 2002).

How can relationships be characterised?

The 'Intervention' approach

- Professional, instrumental
- Task / problem focused
- Change client's acting to well-defined problem: Causes, effects, solutions
- Characteristic of much care work – social work, GP, PHN, educator, etc. (Baart, 2002)

How can relationships be characterised?

The **'presence' approach** (Andries Baart, 2002).

- Quality Time: The worker or volunteer is *'there for others'* without focusing directly on problem solving
- Takes time to get to know the person and their environment deeply
- Strives to affirm the fundamental dignity of the person
- Not problem-focused but may lead to problem solving
- Patience, Unconditional attentiveness and Receptivity
- Engagement and Assumption of (Role-appropriate) Responsibilities

Comparison of Approaches in Youth mentoring

- One to one relationship between an adult volunteer and a young person
- Meet weekly for 2-3 hours over one year or more
- Relationship overseen by a professional caseworker, strict programme practices to ensure safety
- Example: BBBS programme

Methodology: Longitudinal Qualitative Study with Phenomenological Approach

- In-depth semi structured interviews with 11 mentoring matches
- Participants of Interviews: Mentors, Parents and Mentees, Case Workers
- Interviews held during the 1st month and after 5 and 10 months of mentoring involvement
- Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis (IPA, Smith et al., 2012) applied on data received from mentors (30 interviews)

Comparison of Approaches: Helping Attitudes

Intervention Approach

„I thought it is focused on kids from socially weak families who need someone who would go out with him...I expected children who are very introverted, with issues...kind of they'd be fat, with glasses, lisping (laughs), others will be laughing at them...excluded somehow...not the child who has everything and I'd only be there to help his mum with upbringing? No, not at all.“

(Květa, January, 2011).

Presence Approach

„Your aim is just to be yourself, to be a good friend for the child so you don't have to pretend anything...you are as you are and it's the best thing...to be honest and don't pretend anything in front of the child...“

(Ivan, January, 2011)

„ I think it's mostly about relaxation and more like fun for him...the fact that we laugh together a lot, we have fun together and I think he's doing things he wouldn't do otherwise...he can switch off from everything he's experiencing in daily life...I think he can enjoy his childhood in this way...and me with him (Laughs).“

(Sára, December, 2011).

Comparison of Approaches: Satisfaction and Benefits

Intervention Approach: Dissatisfied Rel.

...she got used to things and adapted to the common routines...and I felt like she liked me, she enjoyed the time spent with me but she directly didn't need me...I didn't have much to give her because...I am not her peer...it wasn't that she needed me and took things from me directly...

(Marta, December, 2011).

...this family function completely differently...I could not imagine living there...I just can't make myself like her...we are not on the same level..I am just kind of adult in it...if I was in her skin...I would be bored but she just seems to be happy in it...

(Luisa, December, 2011)

Presence Approach

I just look forward to meeting him, and when I see him in the distance we wave to each other and I think in that moment we tune up into the same wavelength...we share a moment in those moments...similar feelings when we do things together, we are both in it together...I think it's about a play...because I kind of get into the position of the child with him...we just play together...and it's fun...the child's reality where things look different than they are (Laughs).“ (Sára, June, 2011).

‘Because presence practitioners also share the daily, non-problematic and even joyful moments in people’s lives, they make room for the other to shine as a successful and proud person – as joke teller, loving partner, devoted parent...This contrasts sharply with more specialised types of intervention, which involve processes of screening and intake and which apply select remedies to specific problems ... but it is not the way life is lived, often traumatised and chaotic lives.’ (Baart, 2002, p.5)

Conclusions and Recommendations

Reflection on our helping attitudes in services we provide:

- Why did we become social work professionals?
- How do we perceive and approach our clients?

Reflection on our helping relationships we form with clients:

- What kind of relationships do we intend to form?
- What is our impact on clients?
- How do we empathise with clients in our practice?
- Can we be more engaged with our clients in a „presence“ empathetic way?